

James Fergusson (1808-1886): Shaping the history of Indian Architecture

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Accepted: 28 May 2024 / Published online: 30 June 2024

Abstract

James Fergusson, despite contemporary criticism as an Orientalist, stands as a foundational figure in the history of Indian architecture. In the nineteenth century, he pioneered the systematic study of Indian architectural styles, departing from antiquarian approaches to categorize developments based on stylistic evolution. Fergusson's methodology relied on personal observations rather than prior research, setting him apart from the academic norms of his time and enriching his narratives with unique insights. His works remain essential references, detailing architectural features and influencing Western understanding of Indian craftsmanship. However, his Eurocentric biases have drawn scrutiny, highlighting potential oversights of indigenous perspectives. Nonetheless, Fergusson's advocacy for architectural preservation in colonial India underscored his broader impact beyond scholarly circles. Despite the lack of a comprehensive biography, Fergusson's contributions endure through his published works, references, and personal correspondence. His legacy prompts ongoing reassessment within the context of colonial-era scholarship, emphasizing his pivotal role in shaping early narratives of Indian architectural history.

Keywords: James Fergusson, Architectural history, nineteenth century, methodology

Introduction

James Ferguson gave the first description of Indian architecture and, although still immature, attempted to establish the relationship between all races through the study of architecture. He was not an architect, but his deep interest in various forms of architecture in the world produced many scholarly works during his lifetime that made him one of the architectural pioneers in the world. He traveled a long distance and gathered information on historical monuments with his own eyes, interpreted them independently with his theory, did not follow the previous academic views and contextualized the architectural style, though never made him free from the limitation of his time.

James Fergusson, son of Dr. William Ferguson, was born on 22 January 1808 in Ayr, Scotland. His family has strong ties to India, as his elder brother was a partner in the firm of Fairlie, Fergusson and Co. in Calcutta (now Kolkata). After graduation, he came to India to join his family firm but due to this company's failure, Fergusson started a new business in Calcutta and became an indigo planter. Soon after a decade, his family became rich and he lost his interest in business as he preferred to become a scholar in architecture. Then, he was focused on ancient Indian monuments. His passion for heritage led him to become an expert in architecture. His last visit to India was in 1845, but mainly between 1835 and 1842 he traveled a long way through the country with special energy and field notes, his main aim being to write essays, drawings and photographic impressions. Later, he also tried to explain architectural monuments.

Chronology of Fergusson's writings on architecture

His observations on Indian architecture were first published in 1845 in his first book, "Illustrations of the Rock-Cut Temples of India", the text of which named "On the Rock-Cut Temples of India" was read at the Royal Asiatic Society of Great Britain and Ireland in 1844. It contains eighteen large lithographs made by T.C. Dibdin following Ferguson's original sketches.

His next lavish book is a collection of 24 large lithographs of Indian stone architecture, published in 1848 and titled "Picturesque of Ancient Architecture in Hindostan", comprising 70 pages of description. These two publications made him known to the academic community. Ferguson's first theoretical work, "An Historical Inquiry into the True Principles of Beauty in Art, more especially with Reference to Architecture," was published in 1849. As this book criticized the prevailing Euro-centric views, many commercial publishers were not interested in funding Ferguson's books. John Murray, who owned a publishing company that had long distributed many books, helped Ferguson with his later publications.

Ferguson, who wrote the history of world architecture at that time, understood that theoretical writing would not be accepted by people, and followed John Murray's advice and wrote a guide to world architecture from India to Europe. It is his next publication where he followed the geographical order to describe the architecture of various countries. The title of this great volume is "The Illustrated Handbook of Architecture: Being a Concise and Popular Account of the Different Styles of Architecture Prevailing in All Ages and Countries" in two volumes published in 1855. He gathered vast information worldwide and described it in geographical order. Here for the first time, Indian architecture was described in a systematic order. The book covers world architecture, and the order of the first volume being India, China, Western Asia, Egypt, Greece, Rome, Persia and Islam. The second volume introduces European medieval architecture in the order of France, Belgium, Germany, Italy, Portugal, Britain and Northern Europe, and finally adds Byzantine architecture. Considering that half of the book is about Europe, Ferguson can be considered Eurocentric. However, he aims to improve world architecture as thoroughly as possible. This behavior was rare in the 19th century. These two volumes were limited to the ancient and medieval periods. So, he planned to publish another volume dealing with the post-Renaissance architecture. Thus, his next book "History of the Modern Styles of Architecture" was published in 1862, and it was stated in the introduction that this book could be considered the "third volume of the Handbook".

Ten years after the publication of the previous book, as new information and reports on the world architecture continued to accumulate, Ferguson felt the need to create a new edition to include them. As the previous geographical guidebook became a scholastic work, he planned to turn it into a proper history book and make it in chronological order rather than geographical. In his words “if the intention is only to describe particular styles or separate buildings, the topographical arrangement may be found more convenient; but where anything beyond this is attempted, the historical method is only one which enables it to be done.”(Fergusson, 1874, pp. viii-ix). He wanted to shift the architectural description from mere dry information to a more historical arrangement. This resulted two-volume book, "A History of Architecture in All Countries, from the Earliest Times to the Present Day" which one can call the first attempt to write a Universal history of architecture. The first volume was published in 1865, and the second volume, originally planned for the following year, was postponed until 1867. The third volume of the previous book is accepted as the third volume of the History of Architecture. In 1873 he revised "Modern Style", removed the "Ethnography" section, published the second edition of "Modern Style" and wrote in the preface that this edition was 'intended to form the fourth volume of a new edition' of the 'History of Architecture'. He realized that the description of Indian architecture is not fully comprehended in the 'History of Architecture' as he gathered a very large information on it. So, he planned to publish a separate volume on Indian architecture which will be the third volume of 'History of Architecture.' Thus, he published 'The History of Indian and Eastern Architecture' in 1876 with the help of newly added information by the Archaeological Survey of India under its first Director General Alexander Cunningham (1814-1893). Finally, his whole work was published in 2600 pages in four volumes and established him as a true architectural historian. Later, 'The History of Indian and Eastern Architecture' was revised and supplemented by James Burgess and Richard Phené Spiers in 1910 and published in two volumes.

Some of his works on Indian architecture include "The Worship of the Tree and the Serpent" (1868), and his article on "South Indian Architecture" appears in the periodicals of the Institute of British Architects.

Understanding the methodology of his writings

Ferguson attempts to understand Indian architecture through comparison in a global context. This is reflected in his works *History of Architecture in All Countries* (1867) and *Historical Inquiry into the True Principles.....*(1849). His documentation tries to determine the final details of the monument, treating as the most stable source and therefore most reliable way of interpreting culture. It focuses on the artistic process and functionality of the products, as well as time and regional trends. He was not fully concerned about traditional texts and inscriptions. However, he loved Indian mythology and religion, as evident from the Tree and the Serpent Worship (1868). According to him, Egyptian, classical Greek and Indian architecture represented 'true' style and modern art of Europe seen during the revival of the classical and Gothic are 'imitative' style. Ferguson's documentation and description were more precise and historical than the 'picturesque' aquatints and sketches of William Hodges and the Daniells of the preceding century had achieved.

James Fergusson was a businessman but introduced himself as a scholar in India. However, he devoted himself completely to the study of Indian architecture and succeeded in laying the foundation for the study of Indian architecture. The process of developing his own theory of architectural history was influenced by the stylistic and ethnological study of his time. He was greatly influenced by the method adopted by English architect historian Thomas Rickman (1776-1841) (Rickman, 1817). Rickman described the development of the Gothic architecture style through the ages. Fergusson emphasized Rickman's stylistic classification and opined that it would be comparatively effective not only in Britain but even more so in India (Fergusson, 1910, p. xiv). Furthermore, the 19th century's Gothic Revival movement against the previous 'Neo-classicism'

also played a vital role in the writing of Fergusson. The main theme of this movement was to consider the Gothic style as the ‘true’ figure of Christian architecture of that period and the classical style of Greece and Rome was unsuitable. The Gothic revivalists tried to praise the Gothic style of the Middle age and consider it a ‘true principle’ of architecture.¹ However, Fergusson used the phrase ‘true principles’ in his writing but declined to consider the Gothic style as the true architectural style. He pointed out that “my faith in the exclusive pre-eminence of [European] medieval art was first shaken when I became familiar with the splendid remains of the Mogul and Pathan emperors of Agra and Delhi [in India], and saw how many beauties of even the pointed style had been missed in Europe in the Middle Ages.”(Fergusson, 1865, p. vii). He realized that architectural beauty should be determined by its context and said that “after so extended a survey, it was easy to perceive that beauty in architecture did not reside in pointed or in round arches, in bracket capitals or horizontal architraves, but in thoughtful appropriateness of design and intellectual elegance of detail. I became convinced that no form is in itself better than any other, and that in all instances those are best which are most appropriate to the purposes to which they are applied.”(Fergusson, 1865, p. viii). He remarked that a style could be the ‘true principle’ when it goes together with the society and culture of its time. Gothic style was associated with the Middle age and never comported with modern society (Fergusson, 1855, pp. xxv-xxvi). He developed his architectural thoughts through Indian evidence and caused his ideal differences from contemporary European academics. He promoted the study of architecture from mere amusement of the amateur of the 18th century to new philosophical and historical research.

He was also very influenced by the ethnological study or race theories prevailing in his time. He superimposed the race theory on the architectural style and remarked that the Aryans were not the architectural race. He pointed out that “looking on an ancient building, we can not only tell in what state of civilization its builders lived, or how far they were advanced in the arts, but we can almost certainly say also to what race they belonged, and what their affinities were with the other races or tribes of mankind. So far as my knowledge extends, I do not know a single exception to this rule;

and, as far as I can judge, I believe that architecture is in all these instances as correct a test of race as language, and one far more easily applied and understood. Languages alter and become mixed, and when a change has once been established it is extremely difficult to follow it back to its origin and unravel the elements which compose it, but a building once erected stands unchanged to testify to the time when it was built, and the feelings and motives of its builders remain stamped indelibly upon it as long as it lasts”(Fergusson, 1845, p. iii). He discussed four great races who migrated from central Asia to other continents: Turanian, Semitic, Celtic and Aryan. Turanian widely spread from Asia to Africa including Egypt, China, Japan, Mexico, India (Tamil), and Turkey. Similarly, Semitic immigrated to the Middle East. Celts were the most powerful race of the Bronze Age and creators of beautiful architecture in Europe and other countries. Lastly, Aryans invaded Europe, Persia, and India, defeated aboriginal Turanians, and intermixed with them in many countries. He also pointed out that Persian and Indian being Aryan, did not develop architecture. Though Aryan Greeks produced great architecture, they were supposedly mixed with aboriginal Turanians whom they invaded. European architecture also prospered by the Celtic period, after which it declined under the Aryans. Scholars criticized this view as biased by Scottish nationalism as he belongs to Scottish originated from Celts. This entire ethnological concept is highly criticized by contemporary scholars and fully denies the superiority of any race.

Fergusson applied this racial theory in the classification of Indian architecture too. Though he chronologically divided Indian architecture based on religion but he applied the race theory behind this chronology. He described the Buddhist and Jain architecture (Book I and II) as they were the introduced architecture in India being the religion of the Dasyu (aboriginal) race. Then he discussed Hindu architecture in three chronological divisions. Firstly, he placed Southern Dravidian style (book IV) as they belong to aboriginal Turanian which came first to India before the bronze age, then Central Chalukyan Style (book V) which he associated with neither Dravidian nor Aryan but the intermixture of both, and lastly placed Indo-Aryan style (book VI) whom he did not consider architectural race and learn architecture after mixed with aboriginal peoples of India.

Then he placed Islamic architecture (book VII) and architecture beyond India (book VIII).(Fergusson, 1876). This entire view is not accepted now and is highly criticized by later scholars like E B Havell, A. K. Coomaraswamy and others. However, some later scholars like Percy Brown whose book is considered a textbook of the history of Indian architecture follow Fergusson's classification to some extent.

Conclusion

Although his work is more important for the originality and photography (woodcut) of Indian art, it has been criticized by modern scholars. Since he was not interested in literature, he was never interested in the study of Indian art and symbols. He also successfully applied universally valid principles of geological investigation, not only in England but in every country in Europe. However, he could not acknowledge the research initiated by Ram Raz (Raz, 1834). Therefore, he could not understand the symbolism of Indian art. Ferguson's approach was continued and followed in the Indian context by his successors James Burgess, Henry Cousins, Alexander Rea, AH Langhurst and Percy Brown. After the advance of nationalism in the study of Indian art in the 20th century, the history of Indian art and architecture attracted greater attention from some Indian scholars. However, Fergusson's descriptions of early Indian architecture find a systematic way and his use of woodcut photocopies made his books very popular still now. Therefore, recent scholars on Indian art like Pramod Chandra, Partha Mitter, Tapati Guha Thakurata appreciate Fergusson's comprehensive scholarship on Indian architecture though criticized for his classification of it. According to Partha Mitter, "As a writer who covered such a wide span of history, it was inevitable that he would be concerned with a broad conceptual framework. In this too Fergusson differed from the pragmatism of his English colleagues in archaeology."(Mitter, 2013, p. 273) He was the first to write such a Universal history of architecture in English and the only one before Sir Banister Fletches.(Fletcher, 1896)

Notes

ⁱ As one can notice the use of the phrase 'true principles' in the title of the book "The True Principles of Pointed or Christian Architecture" (1841) by Augustus Welby Northmore Pugin. He was a representative of Gothic revival movement in England. Fergusson empathized and borrowed this phrase in his writing.

Bibliography

- Bhattacharya, A. K. (2013). An Appraisal of Approaches to the Study of Ancient Indian Art. In D. C. Ghosh, & R. Sen, *Indian Historiography* (Vol. 2, pp. 1-31). Kolkata: Institute of Historical Studies.
- Chandra, P. (1983). *On the Study of Indian Art*. Cambridge: Harvard University press.
- Fergusson, J. (1845). *Illustrations of the Rock-cut Temples of India*. London: John Weale.
- Fergusson, J. (1849). *An Historical Inquiry into the True Principles of Beauty in Art, more especially with reference to Architecture*. London: Longmans.
- Fergusson, J. (1855). *The Illustrated Handbook of Architecture* (Vol. 1). London: John Murray.
- Fergusson, J. (1865). *A History of Architecture of All Countries* (1st ed., Vol. 1). London: John Murray.
- Fergusson, J. (1874). *History of Architecture in All Countries* (2nd ed., Vol. I). New York: John Murray.
- Fergusson, J. (1876). *History of Indian and Eastern Architecture* (Vol. 3rd of the new edition of the 'History of Architecture'). London: John Murray.
- Fergusson, J. (1910). *History of Indian and Eastern Architecture* (revised ed., Vol. 1). (J. Burgess, & P. Spiers, Eds.) London: John Murray.
- Fletcher, B. (1896). *A history of architecture on the comparative method for the student, craftsman, and amateur*. New York: Charles Scribner's Sons.

Guha-Thakurta, T. (2004). *Monuments, Objects, Histories: Institutions of Art in Colonial and Postcolonial India*. New York: Columbia University Press.

Mitter, P. (2013). *Much Maligned Monsters: History of European Reactions to Indian Art* (3rd ed.). New Delhi: Oxford University Press.

Raz, R. (1834). *Essay on the architecture of the Hindus*. London: Royal Asiatic Society of Great Britan and Ireland.

Rickman, T. (1817). *An Attempt to Discriminate the Styles of English Architecture from the Conquest to the Reformation*. London: John Henry Parker.

Other Sources:

1. Kohane, **Peter**. (2024, July 10) *From Scotland to India: The Sources of James Fergusson's Theory of Architecture's "True Styles"*. Retrieved from <https://journals.openedition.org/abe/5551>
2. Kamiya, Takeo (2024, July 6) *James Fergusson and Indian Architecture*. Retrieved from <http://www.kamit.jp/engl.htm#kami>